

NOTES

Magnetic and Spectral Behaviour of Palladium(II), Platinum(IV) and Ruthenium(III) Complexes with some Tridentate Substituted Thiosemicarbazones

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In a sequence to our earlier reports^{1,2} of transition metal complexes with heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones, we here report the isolation of Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV} and Ru^{III} complexes with recently synthesised tridentate ligands by following the method of Verma³, viz. 1-benzaldehyde-4-thiosalicylamidothiosemicarbazone (C₁₅H₁₄N₄O₂S : HS-SABTZ), 1-benzaldehyde-4-(3-hydroxy-2-naphthamido)thiosemicarbazone (C₁₉H₁₆N₄O₃S : HO-NABTZ) and 1-benzaldehyde-4-(2-hydroxy-3-indomido)thiosemicarbazone (C₁₈H₁₆N₄O₃S : HO-INBTZ) and they are characterised by chemical analysis, molar conductance, magnetic and electronic and ir spectral studies in order to evaluate the stereochemistry of the ligands around the metal ions.

Experimental

[Monochloro-mono(-S-SABTZ)](-O-NABTZ)](-O-INBTZ) Pd^{II}]; [bis(-S-SABTZ)](-O-NABTZ)](-O-INBTZ) Pt^{IV} dichloride]; [bis(-S-SABTZ)](-O-NABTZ)](-O-INBTZ) Ru^{III}] monochloride: The acetonic solution of the ligands (2 mM) was mixed with ethanolic solution of PdCl₂·2H₂O (0.34 g, 2 mM) or chloroplatinic acid (0.41 g, 1 mM) or ruthenium trichloride (0.207 g, 1 mM) and the reaction mixtures were refluxed over steam-bath for ~2 h. Subsequently on cooling, coloured products obtained were filtered, washed with several increments of ethanol and dried completely under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. The products were crystallised with acetone and were found tlc-pure and freely soluble in DMF, DMSO and nitromethane.

In all of the present complexes ionic chlorine was estimated by adding alcoholic solution of AgNO₃ to the isolated and weighed complex, giving a white curdy precipitate and indicating the presence of ionic chlorine outside the coordination sphere. The ionic chlorine % were found quite in good

agreement. Chemicals of AnalaR grade and metal salts of John Matheun, were used. Magnetic, absorption and infrared spectral data were taken as described earlier^{1,2}. The molar conductance values in 10⁻³ M DMF are recorded in the Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The absorption bands from Pd^{II} complexes, viz. 20 800, 23 800 and 28 500 (with HS-SABTZ), 19 800, 21 900 and 26 000 (with HO-NABTZ) and 21 800, 23 000 and 26 500 cm⁻¹ (with HO-INBTZ) are assigned⁴ to spin-allowed transitions, viz. ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g, respectively. The values of μ_{eff}, Δ₁, Δ₂, Δ₃ and LFSE, viz. (0.42, 24 300, 5 000, 4 200 and 83.3), (0.32, 23 300, 4 100, 3 600 and 79.9) and (0.28 B.M., 25 300 cm⁻¹, 3 200 cm⁻¹, 3 000 cm⁻¹ and 86.6 kcal mol⁻¹) from Pd^{II} complexes with proposed ligands HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ and HO-INBTZ, respectively, revealed⁵ square-planer stereochemistry around Pd^{II} metal ion. The large value of Δ₁ for the complex with HO-INBTZ corresponds to a high value of LFSE, which is considered due to larger ligand field-splitting on complexation.

From absorption spectra of Pt^{IV} complexes the bands observed at 19 000, 24 500, 26 300 and 34 700 (HS-SABTZ); 17 500, 18 800, 25 000 and 35 200 (HO-NABTZ) and 17 200, 20 400, 24 700 and 34 800 cm⁻¹ (HO-INBTZ) are tentatively assigned⁶ to ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, ³T_{2g}, ³T_{1g} and ³T_{2g}, respectively, following octahedral field with d⁶ configuration. The values of μ_{eff}, 10Dq, B, β and LFSE are calculated, viz. (2.12, 29 950, 525, 0.59 and 30.06), (1.37, 28 750, 403, 0.56 and 32.86) and (1.37 B.M., 28 450 cm⁻¹, 387 cm⁻¹, 0.55 and 32.52 kcal mol⁻¹) for Pt^{IV} complexes with HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ and HO-INBTZ, respectively, revealed⁶ octahedral stereochemistry. The smaller β values calculated in the range (0.55-0.59) reveal their strong covalent character which is also supported by a small value of molar conductance.

From the present Ru^{III} complexes, the absorption bands observed at 16 950, 19 600 and 23 500 (HS-SABTZ); 16 000, 20 400 and 22 800 (HO-NABTZ) and 17 500, 21 900 and 24 800 cm⁻¹ (HO-INBTZ) are assigned to ²T_{1g} → ²E_g, ²T_{1g} → ²A_{2g} and ²T_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, respectively, by following (t_{2g})⁵(e_g)¹ configuration. The separation energy between two spin-forbidden transitions assigned to ²T_{1g} → ²E_g and ²T_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, corresponds⁴ to 8B. The values of 10Dq have been calculated from the ratio (Dq/B) = 5.1. The energy-difference (E^{*}) between the ground state and first excited state is also calculated

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA FOR Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV} AND Ru^{III} COMPLEXES WITH HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ AND HO-INBTZ

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Molar con- ductance in 10 ⁻³ M DMF Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Ir bands (cm ⁻¹) and tentative assignments*		
				C	S	Cl/N*	Metal/H*	$\nu_{C=N}$ of imine-N	$(\nu_{C=S} + \nu_{C=N} + \gamma_{CN})$	$\nu_{C=S}$
C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (HS-SABTZ)	Light yellow	137	—	54.81 (54.54)	18.54 (19.39)	17.95* (16.96)*	4.31* (4.21)*	1 650s	1 310s	750vs
C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (HO-NABTZ)	Buff yellow	127	—	62.26 (62.63)	9.18 (8.79)	15.64* (15.38)*	4.21* (4.39)*	1 635s	1 300s	760vs
C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (HO-INBTZ)	Yellowish-red	115	—	61.96 (61.53)	9.52 (9.11)	15.27* (15.95)*	4.13* (4.27)*	1 640s	1 395s	755vs
[Pd(-S-SABTZ)Cl]	Orange-red	202	1.43	37.74 (38.30)	14.23 (13.60)	6.32 (7.50)	23.07 (22.63)	1 650s	1 275m	730s
[Pd(-O-NABTZ)Cl]	Dark red	200	5.49	45.78 (45.13)	5.86 (6.33)	6.85 (7.02)	18.90 (18.46)	1 650s	1 275ms	735s
[Pd(-O-INBTZ)Cl]	Dark red	152	0.017	44.32 (43.91)	6.18 (6.50)	6.84 (7.21)	22.25 (21.63)	1 655s	1 270ms	725s
[Pt(S-SABTZ) ₂ Cl ₂]	Orange	120	171.5	41.27 (42.11)	14.35 (14.84)	7.27 (7.56)	24.12 (23.25)	1 635s	1 270ms	740vs
[Pt(-O-NABTZ) ₂ Cl ₂]	Orange	86	183.4	48.78 (49.52)	6.63 (6.95)	7.23 (7.05)	22.12 (21.16)	1 635s	1 265ms	725ms
[Pt(-O-INBTZ) ₂ Cl ₂]	Orange	90	175.2	48.53 (48.27)	6.95 (7.15)	7.64 (7.23)	22.16 (21.79)	1 635s	1 270s	720m
[Ru(-S-SABTZ) ₂ Cl]	Greyish yellow	115	94.52	44.78 (45.31)	15.85 (16.11)	4.72 (4.46)	13.05 (12.72)	1 640s	1 370ms	735s
[Ru(-O-NABTZ) ₂ Cl]	Dull grey	98	101.6	53.14 (52.86)	7.75 (7.42)	4.04 (4.11)	12.03 (11.70)	1 645s	1 360ms	730s
[Ru(-O-INBTZ) ₂ Cl]	Dull grey	105	98.7	50.15 (49.51)	7.52 (7.3)	3.84 (4.06)	12.08 (11.77)	1 645s	1 360ms	735s

* vs=very sharp, s=sharp, m=medium, ms=medium sharp.

by using the relation $E^* = (10Dq - 3F_2 - 20F_4)$ assuming $F_2 = 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $F_4 = 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For the Ru^{III} complexes with HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ and HO-INBTZ, the value of μ_{eff} , 10Dq, B and E* are calculated as (0.25, 41 769, 19 and 21 739), (0.19, 43 400, 850 and 23 370) and (0.31 B.M., 46 512 cm^{-1} , 912 cm^{-1} and 16 482 cm^{-1}), respectively, revealing⁷ inner-orbital low-spin distorted octahedral stereochemistry of the ligands around Ru^{III} metal ion.

The sharp absorption bands observed at ~ 1300 and $\sim 750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands, assigned⁸ to $(\nu_{C=S} + \nu_{C=N} + \gamma_{CN})$ and $\nu_{C=S}$, respectively, are decreased in frequency (by 20-40 cm^{-1}) as well as weakened in intensity, revealing coordination through thio-keto-sulphur atom. The absence of the band observed in free ligands at 2 320 (HS-SABTZ), 3 300 (HO-NABTZ) and 3 180 cm^{-1} (HO-INBTZ) assigned to ν_{SH} , ν_{OH} and ν_{OH} , respectively, ascertain the participation of the sulphur atom of SH group and oxygen atom of OH group through deprotonation on complexation under study. The sharp absorption bands observed at 1 650, 1 635 and 1 640 cm^{-1} (in the free ligands), attributed to $\nu_{C=N}$ of immine-nitrogen do not exhibit any remarkable red/blue shift in frequency as well as decrease in their intensity, indicating non-involvement of immine-nitrogen in coordination. In all of the present complexes, the medium to weak intensity bands observed in the far-ir, region, viz. 550-500, 450-400 and 350-250 cm^{-1} , tentatively assigned⁸ to $\nu_{M-\text{amide-N}}$, ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-Cl} , respectively, also confirm the square-planer and octahedral stereochemistries of

ligands HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ and HO-INBTZ around Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV}, and Ru^{III} metal ions, respectively.

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Studies on Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Gallium(III) by Cationic and Anionic Surfactants and by their Mixtures vis-a-vis the Adsorption Characteristics

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A survey of literature reveals that suppression of polarographic maximum of Ca^{III} by surfactants has not been attempted so far. The present paper reports the results of our investigations on